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THE INDIVIDUALITY AND TRAITS OF CHINESE ETHNIC MUSIC

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Abstract

China is a multi-ethnic country, with 56 ethnic groups each having their own characteristics, and the history of ethnic music has a long history, with unique artistic and aesthetic characteristics. China's ethnic music presents unique features, diverse styles and diverse forms and genres, with strong inclusiveness and development. In the process of historical development, ethnic music has been able to maintain a high degree of consistency between aesthetic characteristics and artistic features, mainly because China's ethnic culture can correctly understand the connotation of ethnic music art. On this basis, this article briefly analyzes the artistic personality and characteristics of China's ethnic music, hoping to effectively promote the sustainable development and innovation of ethnic music culture, and effectively highlight the unique artistic quality of China's ethnic music.

Keywords: ethnic music, artistic personality, traits, diversity, inclusiveness.

1. Concept of Chinese Ethnic Music

Ethnic music refers to ethnic music that is unique, artistic, and humanistic in the historical development process of a certain nation or country. Ethnic music not only includes local and folk music programs and traditional works, but also includes folk music programs or music works adapted from elements, vocal works created according to folk music specifications or forms, and so on. The ethnic music mentioned in this article refers to Chinese ethnic music, which has a diverse and diverse style and a long history of development. Combining the concept of folk music, Chinese ethnic music can be divided into two parts: 1. Traditional ethnic music includes traditional opera and folk songs, quyi, dance and instrumental music, and rap music art forms. For example: Errenzhuang, Beijing Opera, Yue Opera, Pingju, etc., Taiping lyrics and Suzhou Pingtan, Beijing Rhyme Drum, etc. 2. Ethnic music works that combine traditional Chinese music repertoire and creative elements, as well as traditional music forms and specifications. Wang Luobin is known as the Western Song King Wang Luobin's music works, which have strong representativeness. Wang Luobin is particularly fond of Xinjiang music art and has created a large number of classic vocal works based on Xinjiang folk songs, such as "Raise Your Head", "In That Faraway Place", and "Youth Dance". Based on the numerous characteristics mentioned above, it indicates that Chinese ethnic music has strong aesthetic and artistic characteristics.

2. The Artistic Characteristics of Chinese Ethnic Music

(1) Inclusiveness

Chinese ethnic music has artistic characteristics and strong personality, mainly due to its developmental and glorious nature. Whether it is opera, folk songs, or

rap art, there are relatively mature music specifications and forms, but the content is not fixed. Each ethnic music art form will be created in combination with social culture and historical background, so it will be based on the diverse development needs of society, Derived new music tracks and works. For example, during the reign of Emperor Qianlong, the economy was established and gradually developed, and to this day, the repertoire of Peking Opera has gradually enriched and updated without stagnation. The economy has strong artistic specifications and expressive value, with a large number of classic songs, such as "Three Claws", "Yutang Spring", "The Gathering of Heroes", "Picking a Pulley", "Picking up Jade Bracelets", and other new songs that combine the characteristics of the times. For example, Mei Lanfang, a famous theatrical theorist during the Republic of China period, is one of the most representative works of New Beijing Opera, such as "Luoshen", "Tiannu Sanhua", and "Yizhaoma". Whether it is the new Peking Opera repertoire or the significance of its development, it not only enriches the total number of Peking Opera, but also comprehensively improves the scale and level of Peking Opera art from various aspects such as its artistic ideas and concepts, spirit and expression methods, upper forms and costumes, and stage settings. The above are sufficient evidence that China's ethnic music art has strong inclusiveness and development, constantly innovating and developing in the long river of history, and is unique.

2. Diversity

The forms and genres of ethnic music art in China have strong ethnic characteristics and styles, distinct artistic personalities, and are mainly closely related to the cultural and geographical environment. China has a

vast territory and is a multi-ethnic country, with significant differences in geographical environment among different ethnic groups and regions. Therefore, the customs and living habits of different ethnic groups are different. In the daily production and life, ethnic groups and regions have created ethnic music arts with unique ethnic characteristics. For example, Qin Opera in Shaanxi has grand momentum and high voice, while Yueju Opera in the south of the Yangtze River is fresh and soft, Beijing Opera is grand and elegant, and Henan Opera is full of charm. Xinjiang folk songs have strong exotic characteristics, with Mongolian folk songs singing strangely, while Northeast folk songs are warm and straightforward, while Jiangnan folk songs are soft and gentle. From this, it can be seen that the music of 56 ethnic groups in China is showing a diversified development trend, and the development of ethnic music is extremely brilliant.

3. The Attribute Function of Inheriting and Spreading National Values and Culture in Ethnic Music

Values constantly influence people's lives and work, mental state and spirit, cognitive abilities, and so on. Values are the unique value system of various ethnic groups and countries in the historical development process, mainly derived from national culture, also belonging to specific cultures, or the driving force of civilized production and development. Compared to values, cultural connotations are more in line with people's production and life, helping to gradually improve the details and aspects of life, influencing or guiding people's way of life and work. In the current context of globalization, no matter which country attaches great importance to its own civilization history and spiritual culture, especially the shaping and output of values. Although there is no significant correlation between ethnic music and values on the surface, the essence of the two is inseparable and plays an irreplaceable role in the development of Chinese ethnic music. Due to the fact that values are an important aspect of China's spiritual civilization construction, the shaping of values is a policy and administrative policy of the country and government with strong political color. However, political color is not a matter of color, but rather a driving force for promoting China's continuous development. Both ancient and modern ethnic groups have a close relationship between music and political development. Although this correlation is not as direct and specific as other things, it still has an extremely important promoting effect. For example, from the perspective of traditional music ideology, traditional ethnic music must improve people's ideological values in order to reflect the significance and value that ethnic music should have. Analyze values from the perspective of the overall development and strategy of the country, including theory and writing, as well as artistic soft power, such as the development of art and music. Music is the most commonly accepted form of art, and people can directly feel and promote values from it. For example, classical art songs and European classical operas have gradually evolved into the mainstream of world music development through continuous development and innovation. Western mainstream music has swept the world, and

when people's thoughts are influenced by Western music culture, they can also be influenced by the culture represented by Western music. Thus, it subtly affects one's own values and ideological culture, which is the expression of the output and acceptance of values.

The development and inclusiveness of Chinese ethnic music are mainly due to its own aesthetic personality and artistic nature. Due to the different functional attributes and aesthetic standards of music, regardless of which ethnic or national ethnic music art is closely related to aesthetic standards and functional attributes, which are the most basic aesthetic and entertainment functions. Whether ethnic music has the function of inheritance and cultural dissemination, and so on. The ways of thinking and cultural personalities of different ethnic groups and countries are different, so there is a significant difference in the level of recognition of the attributes and functions of ethnic music art. Countries and ethnic groups have different understandings and priorities in the functional attributes of music. For example, ethnic music in Africa is relatively primitive, and its music attribute is entertainment, but it has not been elevated to the aesthetic stage. So there are very few ethnic music cultures in Africa. Chinese ethnic music has strong aesthetic standards and individual characteristics, and entertainment is a music art characteristic of various countries. As a country with a long cultural tradition, China's music aesthetics are no less than other countries. Therefore, China's ethnic music has more requirements for musical rhythm and aesthetics. Since the development of ethnic music to this day, whether from the perspective of ethnic thinking or traditional culture, ethnic music is not a single and boring form of performance, but a cultural carrier for the dissemination of values and ideological and moral norms. It bears the important responsibility and responsibility of disseminating ideological and moral norms and their cultural spirit. Analyzing the historical dynasties and development periods of our country, regardless of the social environment and development background, can prove the coherence and continuity of our national culture, as well as the unique and rich content of our national music culture, with profound connotations, strong aesthetic standards, and three-dimensional aesthetic perception level. For example, when appreciating Beijing Opera, most viewers value the performance of the actors and the plot direction of the opera, so they can feel cultural values from the performance. These connotations and drama are also important criteria for the audience to consider when evaluating music works. Traditional Chinese ethnic music has aesthetic and entertainment characteristics, as well as strong cultural dissemination and carrying functions, so the emphasis on aesthetics and entertainment is incomparable. This is also the most important aspect in the development of music in China, and it is difficult to replace the analysis from multiple perspectives that Chinese ethnic music has more value and role, can bring sensory pleasure to people, and can also improve people's ideological cognition, carrying national emotions and thoughts, values and national cohesion.

Conclusion

In summary, we can see that China is a multi-ethnic country with 56 ethnic groups, each with its own unique music and art styles. However, the aesthetic and artistic characteristics of ethnic music have strong consistency, and it has important functions in cultural dissemination and value carrying. So in the new era, in order to fully utilize China's ethnic music culture, it is necessary to have a correct understanding of ethnic music culture, analyze and explore ethnic music art from a cultural perspective, in order to ensure that China's ethnic music continues to develop and innovate under the wave of multiculturalism, showcasing individual characteristics and cultural attributes. Ethnic music in the development process helps to promote the continuous construction of China's spiritual civilization, which is also the charm and core value of ethnic music art.

4. The Historical Origins of Chinese Ethnic Music Art

China is a country with a long history, with 56 ethnic groups enjoying a vast source of prosperity, laying a solid foundation for the development of ethnic music. During the Western Zhou period, palace music underwent further development and innovation. Western Zhou music was mainly applied to ritual activities, with a huge scale of music activities. During the Spring and Autumn and Warring States periods, society presented a situation of music innovation where hundreds of boats competed for excellence, and music art also underwent further innovative development. During the Han Dynasty, Zhang Qian sent envoys to the Western Regions to facilitate the smooth flow of the Silk Road, and music from various countries blended with each other. The development of Qing commercial music during the Northern and Southern Dynasties, as well as the development of song and dance music during the Sui and Tang dynasties, led to a diversified trend in the development of music in China. During the Song and Yuan dynasties, numerous forms of performance such as Chu palace tunes, zaju, and yuanben emerged. In the embryonic stage of capitalist economy during the Ming and Qing dynasties, folk songs and diversified rap music emerged, such as Northern Drum Ci and Southern Tanci. During the Ming and Qing dynasties, China's ethnic song and dance music underwent certain development and innovation, with Uyghur Mukam, Han Yangge, and Dai Peacock Dance further enriching the forms of ethnic music expression. In the context of modern cultural reform, revolutionary movements drive the continuous development and progress of history. During this period, the characteristics of ethnic music are mainly based on science and democracy as the development trend, such as "Hong Xiuquan Uprising" and "Tian Xin Shun". Local small dramas and Pingju have also been further developed and innovated, such as "Teach Me How to Don't Think of Him" and "Sell Cloth Ballads". After the liberation of China, culture has experienced unprecedented vigorous development, and music popularization activities are being actively held. For example, "Oriental Red" and "Long March Songs" are shining stars in China's music culture. With the gradual development of music activities in the north and south of the Yangtze River, as well as

the artistic performances of ethnic minorities, China's music has presented a scene of competing for excellence.

5. The Path to Promote the Development of National Music Art in China

(1) Resolutely implementing the concept of scientific development

The scientific development concept requires that China must carry out unified and coordinated development in all aspects. Therefore, the inheritance and protection of ethnic music and art must establish a guiding ideology centered on the concept of scientific development, and correctly understand that ethnic music and art are important cultures in China, which helps to promote sustainable economic development in China. Ethnic music culture is the soul that enables a nation to survive and develop, and can also showcase the unique qualities of the nation and the country. Chinese ethnic music art is an important component of China's long history and culture, with strong vitality. It can unite the people of all ethnic groups and promote China's economic development. Therefore, we must implement the concept of scientific development to ensure that the development direction of ethnic music art is correct and feasible.

(2) Carry out folk art and music activities that are close to people's lives

To further inherit and promote ethnic music culture, we should always establish the concept of inheriting and developing ethnic music art, carry out ethnic music art activities that are close to people's lives, and help promote the sustainable development of China's ethnic music art. In the process of development, it is necessary to further create forms of ethnic music expression, so that China's unique ethnic music forms exhibit unique ethnic cultural characteristics, and go deep into the grassroots of the people, close to their daily lives, actively and effectively collect and organize music works with strong ethnic characteristics. This is an important aspect of carrying out ethnic music activities for the inheritance and protection of ethnic music. At present, China's culture is in a diversified development trend. We should combine with the trend of the times to create unique forms of ethnic music expression that are popular among the people and have unique characteristics of the times, to ensure that ethnic music art works have strong development momentum.

(3) Strengthening the Creation of Ethnic Music and Art Works by the Masses

Ethnic music originates from the nation and the people, so diversified mass music and art activities should be held to enable unique music works to be inherited and developed in diverse ethnic activities. We should organize mass music and art performances and various competitions based on the actual situation of the region and ethnic group, and take this as an opportunity to effectively enhance the enthusiasm and enthusiasm of the people for creating folk music and art, which can inject new vitality and vitality into the development of national music in China.

(4) Promoting Ethnic Music Art to the World

Ethnic music belongs to our country, but its development is closely related to the world's development.

In recent years, China's economic openness has gradually accelerated, and international exchanges have become closer. Therefore, in response to the development of ethnic music art, we must effectively promote ethnic music art to the world, which can promote the sustainable development of China's ethnic music. However, there may be certain musical and cultural conflicts in the cultural development process of Eastern and Western ethnic music art, which may even pose a threat to the development of Chinese ethnic music. However, we should correctly understand the advantages and disadvantages of cultural exchange in ethnic music art, closely combine the development situation of Chinese ethnic music art and the development advantages of Western music, and improve and innovate it. Only by truly promoting national music to the world can one give a stunning feeling.

Conclusion

In summary, we can see that ethnicity has a very broad concept in Chinese history and culture, and China's understanding of the term ethnicity is not completely independent and monotonous, nor is it completely distinct. In the era of global multicultural development, every nation and country is seeking individual expression for their own art and culture, so it is also the case in the development process of the Chinese nation, which has a thousand year history and culture.

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